

Improving Image Contrast with 2-Pass Electron Microscopy

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Introduction

Multipass electron microscopy is envisioned to provide increased signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) compared to conventional phase-contrast imaging for a given amount of beam-damage to the sample [1]. In this scheme, a phase object such as a biological sample placed in between two electron mirrors is illuminated M times with the same electrons confined in this electron cavity. Every pass through the sample leads to additional phase accumulation and hence contrast enhancement. As such, demonstration of multipass electron microscopy is perhaps best performed inside a modified TEM at high acceleration voltages (e.g. 200 keV). However, due to various challenges, the most significant of which being the inaccessibility of high-voltage electron mirrors to form the cavity, such an experiment is not trivial. We are currently involved in a collaborative effort towards the construction of a lower-energy (10 keV) analog of this TEM experiment*. In the meantime, however, a carefully designed experiment inside an SEM, may reveal the first signs of electron phase accumulation after passing through a sample twice ($M=2$). This experiment would involve a thin nanofabricated phase-grating placed at the image plane of a tetrode electron mirror inside an SEM. Operating under two-beam condition, observation of increased relative signal intensity in the first-order diffraction spot after two passes would point towards phase accumulation due to $M=2$ multipassing. Analysis of beam-induced damage, however, requires more elaborate experiments. We propose an experiment involving the use of electron-sensitive resist as the sample and the consequent measurement of line-edge roughness after resist development as a proxy for shot noise.

Experimental design

A complete demonstration of multipass electron microscopy must address two aspects: (1) increased image contrast due to additional phase accumulation, (2) reduced beam-induced damage for a fixed SNR. In this section, we address these two aspects in two separate proposed experiments.

Figure 1a shows a schematic of the proposed experiment for demonstration of multipassing in SEM. An electrostatic tetrode electron mirror is placed inside an SEM with its optical axis aligned to that of the SEM objective lens. A nanofabricated phase grating (sample) is placed below the objective lens and overlapping the image plane of the tetrode mirror. The electron beam, focused by the objective lens, would be incident on the phase grating oriented

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at the appropriate tilt to operate under two-beam condition. The 0th and 1st order diffracted beams (with their intensities dependent on the efficiency of the grating [2]) would be reflected by the mirror and re-imaged onto the grating. Passing through the grating again, on the way up, would increase the intensity of the 1st order diffracted beam [2]. In this scheme, we would be relying on the intensity of the diffracted beam as proxy for phase accumulation. We justify this choice in the Discussion section.

To measure the beam intensities, we propose two alternative detection schemes: (1) a copper plate in the form of an annulus, or (2) an annular multi-channel plate (MCP). In both cases, the primary beam would pass through the aperture undetected. In the first approach, only the beam current of the diffracted beam is measured (bucket detector) while in the second approach, an image of the diffraction spot would form onto a scintillator.

Two separate intensity measurements are necessary in order to compare diffracted beam intensities after one and two passes since measuring the beam current or imaging the diffracted beam after the first pass would prevent subsequent measurements following reflection. Therefore, a mechanism for selectively including $M=1$ intensity measurement without altering any other aspect of the experimental setup is necessary. Next, a detector placed above the phase grating and below the SEM objective lens could then measure the intensity of the 1st-order diffracted beam in the far-field after the second pass ($M=2$).

To experimentally demonstrate the damage-reduction aspect of multipass microscopy, we propose a separate experiment. In this experiment, we would expose a thin layer of electron-sensitive resist spun atop an electron-transparent film e.g. SiN in a 2-pass experiment. Next, under similar conditions, but with the mirror turned off, another resist sample would be exposed to the exact same electron dose. An area in the shape of a disk would be exposed in either case. After developing the two samples, we would measure the line edge roughness of the exposed features by either atomic force microscopy or TEM. Since shot noise in electron beam lithography is known to exacerbate line-edge roughness in the exposed features [3], a reduction in line-edge roughness in the sample exposed with the mirror turned on ($M=2$) could point towards higher SNR (i.e. lower damage) of multipass microscopy.

Discussion

An electron plane wave $\psi_i(x, y) = \exp(ikz)$ transmitting through a sinusoidal phase grating described by the transmission function $t(x, y) = \exp(im\sin(2\pi x/p)/2)$ would produce a function $\psi_t(x, y) = \exp(im\sin(2\pi x/p)/2)$ on the other side of the grating ($z = 0$). m and p are the phase contrast and the pitch of the grating, respectively. After the re-imaged wave $\psi_t(x, y)$ transmits through the grating for the second time, the wave $\psi_{tt}(x, y) = \exp(im\sin(2\pi x/p))$ is formed (see Fig. 1a). The accumulated phase shift after two passes is twice that of a single pass. By calculating the square of the Fourier transforms of the waves $\psi_t(x, y)$ and $\psi_{tt}(x, y)$, their far-field intensities could be compared. It can be shown that $|\Psi_{tt_1}|^2 = 4|\Psi_{t_1}|^2$, where Ψ_{tt_1} and Ψ_{t_1} denote the 1st diffraction order of the beam that transmitted through the sample twice and one time, respectively. In other words, by passing the beam through the sample twice and accumulating twice the phase shift, the diffraction intensity quadruples.

Preliminary work

As proof of principle, we obtained simultaneous images of the top and bottom surfaces of a sample in an SEM using a tetrode electron mirror as shown in Fig. 1b-d. The top-surface image is produced as a focused beam is scanned over the top surface of a TEM copper grid with micrometer-sized features comprised of tin nanoparticles and carbon strands. Due to the nature of the sample, at certain pixels, the electrons transmit through the sample-plane undisturbed and downward towards the mirror. They are then reflected by the mirror and re-imaged onto the bottom side of the sample, producing secondary electrons which lead to formation of a scanned image.

The fact that the direct and reflected images shown in Fig. 1b,c do not fully overlap points towards electron optics misalignment, possible sources for which include stage tilt and misalignments in the lens assembly. By adding a tilt stage and by tightening the margins on machining tolerances of the tetrode mirror apertures, we hope to achieve adequate optical alignment necessary for a multipass experiment.

References

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Figure 1. (a) Schematic of the proposed 2-pass electron microscopy inside a conventional SEM. Blue beam represents the primary (zeroth-order) beam. Red beam represents the first-order diffracted beam. Due to the added phase after the second pass through the sinusoidal phase grating, the intensity of the diffracted beam increases. (b),(c) Simultaneous images of top (direct) and bottom (reflected) surfaces of a sample in an SEM using a tetrode mirror. (d) Reflected image of two tin particles wrapped in carbon strands.